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IMPACT OF ORGANIZATIONAL DRIVERS ON EMPLOYEE GREEN BEHAVIOR: A STUDY ON THE SUGAR INDUSTRY OF PAKISTAN

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Abstract

This paper aims to study the impact of organizational drivers on Employee Green Behavior in the sugar industry of Pakistan. We focused on data collected by labour, technical engineers, and chemical engineers' level of employees of sugar the industry. The results obtained are based on information gathered through a closed-ended questionnaire. The research methodology was a quantitative study. The hypotheses were examined via the perspective of regression analysis in the study and found that the independent variables, including Intrafirm communication, Incentive structure & culture, and Transparency and accountability, have a significant and positive impact on EGB. The study recommends future recommendations for research, and addresses the limitations and constraints of the impact of organizational drivers on EGB in this study, using objective measures of green behaviour, and considering individual characteristics and external environmental factors. This study will add to the small body of knowledge on the influence of organizational factors on employees' behaviour toward the environment, particularly in the context of Pakistan's sugar business. The purpose of the study is to provide academics, policymakers, and business leaders with recommendations on how to advance environmentally responsible corporate practices. It also identifies the challenges and opportunities for improving employees' green behaviour in the sugar industry in Pakistan, which can be used for developing strategies to enhance the industry's sustainability. Overall, the findings can assist organizations in the sugar industry and other industries in designing and implementing effective strategies to promote green behaviour among employees, contributing to environmental sustainability and profitability.

Keywords: Management, Psychological, Environmental Knowledge, Organizational

1. Introduction

The issues of environmental contamination and ethical resource use have risen to the top of international politics because of a lack of resources and a public consciousness of the risks of pollution. Long-term economic growth is in opposition to attempts to protect the environment and preserve natural resources (Song, Yu, & Xu, 2021). The continual challenge of striking a balance between economic progress and excessive resource use forces businesses to engage in high-value, environmentally responsible operations (Munawar, Yousaf, Ahmed, & Rehman, 2022). To lessen the effects of these barriers, deploying strategies like green supply chain management, green supply chain innovation, and other similar techniques is necessary. Sustainable development actually depends on green innovation, such as solutions for reducing energy use, preventing pollution, and recycling garbage (Jehan, Hussai, Batool, & Imran, 2020). But as firms embrace environmentally friendly innovations and sustainable methods on their own and in collaboration with other companies along the supply chain, technological hurdles grow. Human resource (HR) strategies that are focused on gaining a competitive edge and enhancing environmental and commercial performance are employed to address these issues (Al-Minhas, Ndubisi, & Barrane, 2020). Sustainability has gotten a lot of attention in recent years, and organizations are putting more and more emphasis on how they affect the environment (Mahmood, Ahmed, & Philbin, 2022). One of the most important things for sustainable growth is for employees to act in ways that are good for the environment. So, it's important to find out what makes employees in businesses act in a green way (Pham, Hoang, & Phan, 2020). Due to the demand from both the interior and exterior of an organization to adopt and implement environmentally responsible business practices, businesses must find

solutions to enhance their competitive advantage, economic performance, and environmental performance. This consists of green supply chain management, green technologies, and green innovation (Mahmood et al., 2022). Reducing energy consumption and pollution emissions, reusing materials, conserving natural resources, and creating environmentally beneficial products are examples of green innovation. The term "green innovation" can also refer to the integration of environmentally responsible product and procedure developments.

Problem Statement

A significant contributor to Pakistan's economy, the sugar industry employs many individuals. Nonetheless, industry is a major source of environmental degradation. In recent years, the government of Pakistan has enacted a few environmental regulations to regulate sugar industry pollution. However, it is unclear how these regulations affect the green behavior of industry employees. The research will examine the status of green behavior among employees in Pakistan's sugar industry as well as the influence of organizational drivers on their behavior. In addition, the research will determine the obstacles that stand in the way of improving green behavior in the workplace as well as the opportunities that exist.

Significance and Scope

The findings of this study will add to the small body of knowledge on the influence of organizational factors on employees' behavior toward the environment, particularly in the context of Pakistan's sugar business. The purpose of the study is to provide academics, policymakers, and business leaders with recommendations on how to advance environmentally responsible corporate practices. The study will also identify the challenges and opportunities for improving employees' green behavior in the sugar industry in Pakistan, which can be used as a basis for developing strategies to enhance the

industry's sustainability. The study can serve as a point of reference for future investigations into employee behavior and environmental sustainability in relation to the sugar industry. So, the goal of this study is to look into how organizational factors affect employee green behavior in the sugar industry of Pakistan. Organizational drivers are factors such as organizational culture, leadership, policies, and practices that motivate employees to adopt environmentally friendly behaviors.

Research Questions

- 1:** Does intrafirm communication have significant impact on Employee Green Behavior (EGB)?
- 2:** Whether Incentive structure & culture have significant impact on Employee Green Behavior (EGB)?
- 3:** Is there any impact of Transparency & Accountability on Employee Green Behavior (EGB)?

Research Objectives

1. To evaluate the impact of intrafirm communication on Employee Green Behavior (EGB)
2. To evaluate the impact of Incentive structure & culture on Employee Green Behavior (EGB)
3. To evaluate the impact of Transparency and accountability on Employee Green Behavior (EGB)

Hypothesis

- H1:** Impact of intrafirm communication on Employee Green Behavior (EGB)
- H2:** Impact of Incentive structure & culture on Employee Green Behavior (EGB)
- H3:** Impact of Transparency & Accountability on Employee Green Behavior (EGB)

Delimitations

The study on the impact of organizational drivers on Employee Green Behavior (EGB) in the sugar industry of Pakistan has several limitations. First, the findings may not be applicable to employees in other industries or different job roles. Second, the research methodology relies on a quantitative

approach, which may limit the depth of understanding and be subject to response bias. Third, the study is geographically confined to the sugar industry in Pakistan, and contextual factors may differ in other industries or countries. Furthermore, the study focuses on specific organizational drivers and does not consider other potential influences on EGB. Self-reported measures and subjective questionnaires may introduce bias or misinterpretation of behavior. The study lacks a specified time frame, neglecting the temporal aspect of organizational drivers on EGB. Resource constraints and the absence of external environmental factors further limit the scope and depth of the research. Recommendations for future studies include exploring different industries and countries, utilizing objective measures, and considering individual characteristics and external factors.

Research Methodology

The study utilized a non-probability convenience sampling method to collect data from employees in the sugar industry of Pakistan, with 350 questionnaires distributed and analyzed using SPSS software.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Background

The theory of planned behavior has been used extensively to explain human behavior in a variety of contexts, with the argument that behavioral intention is influenced by attitude, which in turn influences behavior (Abadiyah, Eliyana, & Sridadi, 2020). It asserts that a person's behavioral intention accurately predicts their behavior and is therefore acknowledged as a potent internal catalyst for any action. In this regard, it is one of the most plausible models for explaining environmental behavior, where environmental behavioral intention represents a person's propensity to engage in environmental behavior and their apparent subjective awareness of environmental activity. Human behavior has been the

primary focus of the Theory of Planned Behavior, as opposed to organizational perspectives. To surmount this limitation of TPB, this research also incorporates Organizational Support Theory (Aggarwal & Agarwala, 2021).

The organizational support theory Abbas and Dogan (2022) recognizes that it provides a method for determining how much a company values their contribution and supports them because employees care more about how they are treated in the workplace. There is evidence that perceived organizational support positively influences environmental management employees' success, effort, and motivation (Bashirun & Noranee, 2020). GPOS refers to an employee's perception of the value of their participation in the organization's green initiatives. Consequently, it is possible to contend that a company's treatment of its employees reveals its environmental orientation. This study employs organizational support theory to illustrate how GPOS moderates the relationship between employee environmental behavioral intention and environmental behavioural behavior (EGB) (Junsheng, Masud, Akhtar, & Rana, 2020). Another definition of sustainable development is development and progress that satisfies the requirements of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Encourage environmental protection attitudes by fostering vigilant attitudes and creating motivations, opportunities, training, and awareness. Climate-representative environmental benefit assumptions play a central role in motivating EGBs. Research demonstrates that dynamic, engaged, and well-trained employees engage in organizational behavior's that motivate environmental performance (Norton, Parker, Davis, Russell, & Ashkanasy, 2018). In addition, the environmentally responsible behaviour of our employees affords them the opportunity to participate in the independent

direction and guide decision-making in order to facilitate the implementation of environmental performance programs through ETUC. Research indicates that HR Driver practices affect employee motivation and commitment to organizational objectives. Long-term performance Aggarwal and Agarwala (2022) was the first to introduce the sustainability concept, which is supported by governments and scientists. Generally speaking, sustainable development is "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the needs of future generations." In addition, the most widely accepted principle of sustainable performance (SP) has three components: economic, social, and environmental performance. Financial responses represent economic performance, environmental responses represent environmental performance, and stakeholder interests represent social performance. Social sustainability refers to the quality of human systems based on various ethical principles, such as fairness, impartiality, and participation.

2.2 Organizational Drivers

Organization Drivers are accustomed to creating the necessary supports and infrastructures for new programs and innovations to flourish. It may be necessary to develop these supports at both the building and district levels.

2.2.1 Intra-firm Communication

Sharma, Kundu, Rana, and Sharma (2023) highlighted that the effectiveness of intra-company communication is another important internal firm characteristic. Internal knowledge transfers within a company are frequently difficult or difficult to achieve, and suboptimal internal knowledge transfers can help to explain firm behavior such as less innovation. Inadequate information transfer within a company may also account for the unintentional greenwashing of brown companies, indicating a lack of communication between

the marketing/PR department and the production, packaging, or product development departments. If all other factors are equal, companies are more likely to engage in greenwashing. For instance, inadequate or nonexistent communication with a product development department, packaging department, or supplier of a product's components may cause a marketing or public relations department to exaggerate a product's greenness. Organizational scholars have analyzed factors that inhibit subunits' knowledge sharing, such as the absence of direct relationships and extensive communication between subunit members. According to the literature on product innovation that focuses on the dissemination of knowledge, close and frequent interactions between R&D and other functions contribute to project success. Applying this concept to the context of greenwashing, we can hypothesize that the lack of frequent and close communication between corporate departments such as marketing and product development may be a significant contributor to greenwashing increase (Pan, Abbas, Álvarez-Otero, Khan, & Cai, 2022). The regulatory environment influences not only the efficiency of an organization's internal communication, but also its incentive structure and culture of ethics. In less regulated environments, businesses can design organizational features such as incentive structures and ethical climates to minimize greenwashing, as well as improve the efficacy of corporate communications to reduce the likelihood of corporate involvement. Few incentives exist to justify implementing a process that does. Greenwashing (Toy et al., 2017).

2.2.2 Organizational Incentive Culture & Structure

An organizational culture incites normal belief. So, every specialist has a motivation to work (freely across specialists). Hence, with drivers, in assumption, most specialists have the drive to work and think almost certainly, most have a motivation to

work and think, all things considered, most (Mehta & Mehta, 2017). To gain insight into how an organization's culture affects performance, incentive structure & and culture have been observed, as the monetary and non-monetary values inspire the employees towards growth and optimal organization performance.

2.3 Transparency and Accountability

Transparency and accountability are two essential concepts that can influence green behavior among employees (Armstrong, 2005). Transparency refers to the disclosure of information, which can help employees understand their organization's environmental impact and how it is addressing sustainability challenges. Accountability, on the other hand, refers to the responsibility an organization has to stakeholders for its actions, including its environmental impact.

2.4 Employee Green Behavior

Depending on the context, "green behaviors" of employees are "scalable acts and behaviors that employees engage in that are related to environmental sustainability and either contribute to or detract from it" (Unsworth, Davis, Russell, & Bretter, 2021). Our definition is purposely dosed to modern conceptions of work performance by emphasizing employee behaviors and activities (rather than the outcomes of such actions. As organizations place a greater emphasis on environmental performance alongside economic performance, we argue that individual-level models of job performance should incorporate employees' green behaviors. Corporate environmental performance, at the organizational level, is the degree of success with which corporations manage natural resources in the creation, manufacture, distribution, and eventual disposal of their products and services. As a result, organizational environmental performance comprises proactive initiatives as well as the environmental "footprint" (i.e.,

ecological impact) of operations (AISuwaidi, Eid, & Agag, 2021).

3. Research Methodology

The research targeted employees within the sugar industries of Pakistan. To obtain a sample, the study utilized the non-probability method known as convenience sampling. This approach involves selecting participants who are easily accessible or reachable within a particular group. Without imposing any additional requirements, the sample was drawn from the primary data source that was readily available for the research. A total of 350 questionnaires, designed in a closed-ended format, were distributed among respondents. The data collection process involved a quantitative approach, utilizing a Likert Scale that was adapted from previous studies. Copies of the questionnaires were disseminated to employees working in sugar industries located in the Lahore district of Pakistan. Subsequently, the collected data was analyzed using SPSS Software Version 22. However, in the methodology section, more intricate details regarding the specific steps and processes involved in the convenience sampling approach could be incorporated to provide a clearer understanding of how the sample was actually gathered from the easily accessible group.

Hypotheses Development

- H1:** Impact of interfirm communication on Employee Green Behavior (EGB)
- H2:** Impact of Incentive structure & culture on Employee Green Behavior (EGB)
- H3:** Impact of Transparency & Accountability on Employee Green Behavior (EGB)

Table 1. Measurement Scales

Constructs	No of items	Scale- Type	Scale Range	Adopted/Adapted
Intrafirm Communication	5	5 – Point Likert Type Scale	1 (agree) to 5 (strongly Disagree)	Adopted
Incentive structure & Culture	5	5 – Point Likert Type Scale	1 (agree) to 5 (strongly Disagree)	Adopted
Transparency & accountability	6	5 – Point Likert Type Scale	1 (agree) to 5 (strongly Disagree)	Adapted
Employee Green Behaviour	10	5 – Point Likert Type Scale	1 (agree) to 5 (strongly Disagree)	Adopted

4. Data Analysis

This section included Reliability analysis, correlational analysis, and regression analysis.

4.1 Reliability Analysis

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.949	26

In this study, an examination was conducted to assess the influence of organizational drivers on employee green behavior. A total of 350 respondents participated by completing the questionnaire, with 270 of these submissions deemed valid and included in the study's analysis. The collected data were processed using SPSS, employing suitable statistical methodologies. The calculated overall Alpha (Cronbach's alpha) for the study yielded a robust value of 0.949%, underscoring the questionnaire's exceptional validity, consistency, and user-friendliness. Notably, each variable's individual Cronbach's alpha value exhibited satisfactory results, thus confirming the questionnaire's reliability for the study's intended purposes.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

		TransAcc	IntFC	Incen	EmGB
TransAcc	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	270			
IntFC	Pearson Correlation	.735**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
	N	270	270		
Incen	Pearson Correlation	.740**	.754**	1	.670**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	270	270	270	269
EmGB	Pearson Correlation	.686**	.640**	.670**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	269	269	269	269

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

**** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

The correlation between variables within the regression model is presented in the "Correlation" table. This correlation model serves to explore the interconnections among the variables investigated in this study. The table illustrates that all variables exhibit noteworthy positive correlations. To illustrate, considering the associations involving transparency & accountability, incentive structure & culture, and intrafirm communication, the correlation coefficient values for R demonstrate strong positive correlations at 0.735, 0.740, and 0.686, respectively. The statistically significant p-value of 0.000 validates the substantial positive relationship between these variables.

4.3 Regression Analysis

Sr.	Hypothesis	F-value (619.410)	R ² (.875)			Accepted/Rejected
		t-value	St. Coefficient (Beta)	p-value		
H1	Impact of intrafirm communication on Employee Green Behaviour (EGB)	12.360	.458	.000	Accepted	
H2	Impact of Incentive structure & culture on Employee Green Behaviour (EGB)	-9.285	-.385	.000	Accepted	
H3	Impact of Transparency & Accountability on Employee Green Behaviour (EGB)	18.833	.845	.000	Accepted	

The table provided offers insights into the outcomes of the hypothesis-testing regression analysis. The adjusted R² value of the model stands at 87%, while the R² value is recorded as 0.936. This observation highlights a 13% variance among the dependent variables within this model. Notably, 13% of the variation in dependent variables remains unexplained by the independent variables under study.

The F-statistics value within this model is calculated as 619.410, surpassing the minimum acceptable threshold of 3.96. This substantiates the model's appropriateness, leading to the acceptance of Hypothesis 1.

Digging deeper into the results, the coefficient of Incentive structure & culture is represented by a negative beta value of -

0.385, with a p-value of 0.000. This indicates that a positive shift in Incentive structure & culture significantly impacts Employee Green Behavior (EGB). Specifically, a one-unit increase in Incentive structure & culture corresponds to a 0.385-unit reduction in EGB. Conversely, intrafirm communication boasts a positive beta value of 0.458, accompanied by a p-value of 0.000. This points to the meaningful influence of positive shifts in intrafirm communication on EGB. Such a movement enhances Employee Green Behavior, as indicated by the beta value.

Furthermore, the coefficient value for transparency & accountability registers an R-value of 0.845, accompanied by a p-value of 0.000. This corroborates the affirmative and statistically significant impact of transparency & accountability on EGB. Hence, Hypotheses 1, 2, and 3 all demonstrate a positive and substantial influence on Employee Green Behavior, collectively contributing to their acceptance. In essence, the regression analysis underscores the affirmative relationships between the variables studied and Employee Green Behavior. The documented results firmly support the positive influences of Incentive structure & culture, intrafirm communication, and transparency & accountability on EGB, validating the acceptance of all the stated hypotheses.

Finding & Discussion

Environmental contamination and sustainable resource usage have risen to the status of global issues of paramount importance due to worries over the environment and the scarcity of available resources. Extensive economic growth is incompatible with conservation of natural resources and gradual pollution lessening. Employees in the sugar industry in Pakistan were also surveyed directly to provide additional original data. After data collection, a reliability analysis was conducted to confirm the questionnaire's validity. In addition to using frequency distribution to examine the

percentages of respondents in each category, we also examined the proportions of respondents using frequency distribution. In addition, correlation and regression analyses are employed to investigate the causal relationship and relationship between variables. The findings revealed a positive relationship between the independent variables Organizational Drivers (Intrafirm communication, incentive structure & culture, & Transparency & Accountability) and the dependent variable (EGB). The correlation analysis revealed that Transparency & Accountability has a direct relationship with EGB, which means that if Transparency & Accountability increases, EGB also increases. Similarly, Intrafirm communication and incentive structure & culture were found to have a positive relationship with EGB, indicating that an increase in incentive structure and culture or intrafirm communication can lead to an increase in employee green behavior. The present study demonstrates that the independent variables show a significant impact on EGB. The results indicated that Incentive structure and culture has a negative coefficient and a significant effect on EGB, implying that an increase in incentives may result in a decrease in employee green behavior. Similarly, the impact of intrafirm communication on Employee Green behaviors has a positive significant effect which implies that increase in intrafirm communication also increases the effect of Employee Green Behavior and decrease in intrafirm communication also decrease the effect of Employee Green Behavior. The results showed that organizational driver transparency & accountability has a positive coefficient value and implies a significant effect on Employee Green Behavior, which indicates any change in transparency & accountability will change the increase and decrease in Employee Green Behavior.

Limitations

The present study shows the number of limitations, and constraints that need very careful demonstration and consideration when interpretation the results of findings. The study was constrained to the sugar industry in Pakistan, thereby restricting the generalizability of the results to other nations and industries. The research utilized a cross-sectional methodology, which restricts the ability to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Thirdly, the utilization of self-reported data may have potentially introduced response bias or social desirability bias into the study. Furthermore, the research failed to consider other potential variables, such as individual traits or external environmental factors, that could potentially impact an employee's pro-environmental conduct.

Recommendations

Considering the limitations of this study, there exist a number of suggestions for prospective research. To enhance the generalizability of the results, forthcoming studies may investigate the impact of organizational drivers on the employee green behavior in diverse sectors and nations. Furthermore, the establishment of causality between the independent and dependent variables could be achieved through the implementation of longitudinal studies. Subsequently, forthcoming research endeavors may consider implementing impartial metrics to assess employee green behavior, as opposed to relying on self-reported information, in order to mitigate potential response bias. Subsequently, it is recommended that forthcoming studies explore personal attributes, such as personality traits and environmental attitudes, as well as external factors, such as regulations and policies that may impact the employee's green behavior. Finally, future studies could explore the effectiveness of interventions such as training programs,

incentives, and feedback systems in promoting employee green behavior in organizations.

Conclusion

The study found that organizational drivers have a significant impact on employee green behavior in the sugar industry in Pakistan. The results showed that an increase in incentive structure and culture, intrafirm communication, transparency, and accountability can lead to an increase in employee green behavior. These findings can be useful for organizations in the sugar industry in Pakistan and other industries to design and implement effective strategies to promote green behavior among employees, which can lead to improved environmental sustainability and profitability.

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